

AI-assistant for intelligent design of controllers in power systems

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ABSTRACT

The increasing penetration of renewable energy sources in power systems has heightened the importance of grid-forming (GFM) converters, which emulate the dynamic behavior of synchronous machines and are crucial for ensuring stability in converter-dominated grids. However, the complexity of modern grids calls for innovative control mechanisms to unlock the full potential of GFM technology. This work presents a novel automated framework for control design in power systems. Simulated annealing is used to evolve the structural design of control systems represented as graph-based models. The method achieves greater flexibility by using control graphs instead of traditional tree-based representations, supporting complex feedback loop configurations. A simplification process is also included to reduce complexity and improve interpretability, ensuring practical applicability. Validation on a two-generator power system with one GFM converter demonstrates the method's ability to design robust controllers that enhance system stability, achieving better performance metrics, such as smoother frequency responses with significantly reduced frequency deviations compared to benchmark configurations. The improved frequency response arises from differing terminal angle profiles, enabling faster, stronger power responses that quickly arrest frequency deviations during disturbances.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and motivation

Throughout the last decades, converter control has been a topic of growing importance in power system stability and control [1]. Among many ideas (e.g., frequency-sensitive modes, fast frequency response, hidden inertia), the study of grid-forming (GFM) control has fostered the most attention due to its promising characteristics, which have long been seen as the key enabler to increasing the share of converter-based generation in the energy mix [2]. This control differentiates itself from others by regulating the active/reactive power through a direct control of voltage magnitude and angle at the converter connection point [3]. To achieve this direct generation of the voltage references from the active/reactive power, a loop often denominated as primary control/outer loop [3,4] is used. Multiple control architectures have been proposed for this loop [5], with the most notable being Virtual Synchronous Machine (VSM), droop control, virtual oscillator control, and matching control [5]. Nevertheless, this loop's refinement is far from complete, as researchers continuously propose new variations, drawing on their creativity and accumulated expertise. Current research avenues

include adaptations to the active power control loop, such as incorporating a lead-lag block in VSMS, introducing adaptive control for GFM parameters, and defining GFM control as a multi-input and multi-output system [3]. Still, the potential for redesigning this control continues to expand, suggesting that only a fraction of GFM converters' ability to surpass synchronous machines has been realized. This constant search for the best control design of the GFM primary control loop brings up the perfect opportunity for the use of ML methodologies that can intelligently search through thousands of combinations by leveraging the feedback provided by an existing digital environment of the dynamics of the converter.

The ongoing pursuit of optimal control designs for the GFM primary control loop presents an ideal opportunity for the use of data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) methodologies that can efficiently search through the vast design space (e.g., with thousands of combinations) by leveraging the feedback provided by a digital environment that simulates the dynamic behavior of the converter. This approach accelerates and automates the discovery process and enhances the precision and adaptability of control strategies, pushing the boundaries of what is achievable with GFM converters. To achieve this goal, this work integrates a

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Nomenclature

AI	Artificial Intelligence	ML	Machine Learning
ANN	Artificial Neural Network	PID	Proportional Integral Derivative
CG	Control Graph	PS-CDA	Power Systems Control Design Assistant
EA	Evolutionary Algorithm	PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
GFM	Grid-forming	SA	Simulated Annealing
GP	Genetic Programming	SMC	Stability Margin Criterion
		VSM	Virtual Synchronous Machine

meta-heuristic optimization approach with a graph-based representation of the control system, creating a framework that evolves and learns from data (and feedback) generated within a digital environment.

1.2. Literature review

Evolutionary-based strategies have been extensively studied and widely applied in control systems engineering, particularly in controller design. Evolutionary algorithms (EAs) have proven effective for parameter optimization, structural design, and model identification. For example, EAs have been employed to fine-tune proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers and to determine optimal control sequences in model-based predictive control [6].

Among these approaches, genetic programming (GP) stands out for its ability to automatically optimize both the topology (e.g., using symbolic equation representations) and parameter values of controllers. GP represents block diagrams using a tree-based architecture, where nodes from a predefined function library correspond to the system's building blocks, and branches define the interconnections. This method allows for simultaneous parameter estimation and model structure identification. For instance, the inclusion of feedback loops in GP-designed controllers was demonstrated in [7], whereas [8] lacked this feature.

Applications of GP in the literature include multi-objective GP for determining the optimal transfer function structure in uncertain systems [9], integration with formal verification tools like satisfiability modulo theories (SMT) solvers to synthesize control Lyapunov functions [10], and the use of a modified Cartesian GP incorporating the principle of small variations for the automatic synthesis of stabilization systems [11]. The conventional GP method for controller design has been further enhanced in [12] by incorporating domain-specific elements, including time-domain operators and customized fitness functions that evaluate key criteria such as performance, robustness, and practical implementation feasibility. GP has also been integrated with reinforcement learning for autonomously generating and evaluating power converter topologies based on user-defined design requirements [13].

An alternative to conventional model-driven controllers lies in data-driven intelligent control systems, such as fuzzy control, which allows the incorporation of expert knowledge into the design, and artificial neural networks (ANNs) that can be trained in a reinforcement learning fashion [14]. A comprehensive literature review can be found in [15]. However, regulatory frameworks, such as the European Union AI Act [16], impose strict requirements for AI in high-risk sectors, including interpretability and transparency. In this context, model-driven approaches that can learn and evolve from data offer a compelling alternative to purely data-driven models. Furthermore, models like fuzzy controllers and ANNs require ongoing maintenance to address challenges such as data changes resulting from power system modifications (e.g., concept drift) and ensure robustness and safety against various events, including perturbations or attacks targeting the input, output, or AI model. Conventional controllers can be augmented with data-driven learning capabilities to balance interpretability and adaptability. This hybrid approach preserves interpretability and human oversight and meets the stringent demands of critical infrastructure systems.

Meta-heuristics have also been widely applied to address control system design challenges. For instance, simulated annealing (SA) was employed in [17] for the robust design of a power system stabilizer. The problem was formulated as an optimization task, where SA was used to identify the optimal settings for the stabilizer parameters. Similarly, SA was applied in [18] to tune PID controllers and optimize load frequency control and automatic voltage regulation in multi-source multi-area power systems. Additionally, in [19], several meta-heuristic algorithms were compared for optimizing the coefficients of two controllers in an average current mode-controlled boost power factor correction circuit. In contrast to the data-driven GP approach, which simultaneously learns system dynamics and controller structures from data, meta-heuristics are primarily employed within a model-driven framework. They are used to optimize pre-defined system parameters or identify system models based on a mathematical representation.

1.3. Contributions

The primary contribution of this work is the development of an automatic data-driven learning process for generating small-/medium-scale controllers for different power system elements. This is achieved using a meta-heuristic algorithm – specifically, SA – as a search engine that evolves the control system. The knowledge is represented as a graph and refined through feedback from a digital replica of the system, which accurately replicates its dynamic behavior. This approach leverages existing principles of traditional model-driven controllers while enhancing their performance through data-driven learning.

This work stands out from previous research through several key contributions. First, SA is employed instead of GP, and the representation of block diagrams is achieved using a control graph (CG) rather than a tree-based architecture, as used in [6,9,10]. The CG representation offers greater flexibility in generating structures. For instance, while creating a feedback loop in tree-based architectures requires a specialized block, in CG, the feedback loop is naturally represented as an additional edge in the graph. Moreover, the CG representation preserves the structure of the block diagram, providing higher interpretability compared to a tree-based representation.

In contrast to the classical Genetic Programming (GP) method, which is a single-level algorithm that iteratively modifies the entire tree structure, simultaneously changing functional blocks (such as integrators, lead functions, and PIDs) and their parameters (gains, time constants, etc.), the proposed method employs a bi-level algorithm [20]. This bi-level approach separately adjusts the topological structure of the graph and its numerical constants at each iteration. Specifically, a parameter tuning phase is performed whenever a structural change occurs (e.g., changing functional blocks or adding new connections). This step ensures a fair comparison between solutions and prevents suitable block diagram topologies from being dismissed due to inadequate parameter adjustment. To reduce the computational time, parameter tuning techniques that use frequency domain analysis are adopted, rather than relying on time-domain simulations.

Furthermore, unlike methodologies that generate controllers using “black-box” models such as ANN [14,15], this work introduces two significant advancements. It preserves the logic of block diagrams, which

facilitates the use of well-established control analysis methods rooted in classical control theory and enables easier interpretation of the controller’s behavior. Additionally, it fosters cooperative learning between humans and AI. This can occur at the initialization phase, where an operator can define an initial controller based on prior system knowledge or existing designs, or during the evolution process, where the operator can provide additional guidance to refine the search algorithm’s outcomes. Conversely, the end-to-end design of complex and extensive control systems (e.g., autonomous driving and drone navigation) may prove to be too large a task for methods of automatic block diagram construction, such as GP or the proposed method. This is an area where ANNs have repeatedly demonstrated their effectiveness [21]. To successfully address tasks of this nature, human intervention is necessary to divide the large control system into smaller, more manageable sections. Subsequently, GP or SA can be employed to generate the control loops for these individual sections.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the methodology of the control design assistant, detailing the process of evolving controllers from data. Section 3 presents numerical results for two case studies: a small illustrative example of a system with a hydropower unit supplying a load in islanded operation and a simplified system where a GFM converter is connected to an equivalent representation of the power system. Finally, Section 4 provides the conclusions and potential directions for future research.

2. Power system control design assistant (PS-CDA)

The Power System Control Design Assistant (PS-CDA) is a tool designed to provide system operators and engineers with intuitive and efficient means to generate controllers for various applications within the power system domain. This methodology employs a bi-level meta-heuristic algorithm to evolve a graph-based representation of block diagrams iteratively. Feedback on the quality of the controller is obtained through interactions with a digital environment that simulates the dynamic behavior of the real control system. This section elaborates on the core components of the PS-CDA methodology. It demonstrates its application with an illustrative example: the design of a controller for the governor of hydro units, a simple yet classical case in power system control design.

2.1. Knowledge representation: control blocks

The chosen representation for block diagrams is based on signal-flow graphs [22], referred to in this work as control graphs (CGs). Unlike traditional signal-flow graphs, this approach introduces a novel variation: the nodes of the CG represent not only the functional blocks of the block diagram (e.g. gains, integrators, first-order transfer functions, etc.) but

Table 1
Transfer functions library for each block.

Code	Function name	Transfer function	Parameters
1	Gain	K	K
2	Integrator	$\frac{1}{s}$	\emptyset
3	Derivator	s	\emptyset
4	PI	$K_p + \frac{K_i}{s}$	K_p, K_i
5	PD	$K_p + K_d s$	K_p, K_d
6	PID	$K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s$	K_p, K_i, K_d
7	First order	$\frac{1}{\tau s + 1}$	τ
8	Second order	$\frac{\omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}$	ω_n, ζ
9	Lead	$\frac{\tau s + 1}{\alpha \tau s + 1}$	τ, α
10	Lag	$\frac{\alpha \tau s + 1}{\tau s + 1}$	τ, α
11	VSM	$\frac{1}{2Hs + D}$	H, D

also the sum blocks and the points with multiple connections. This enhancement is essential as it allows new elements to be placed anywhere within the graph, significantly increasing the flexibility of the design strategy. The edges of the graph represent the connections between the functional blocks.

The graph is divided into three sections: the base, the branches, and the feedback. The base corresponds to the direct path between the input and the output of the CG. The branch section includes the blocks connected to the base in the forward direction. Finally, the feedback section contains the feedback loops. An example of representation can be found in Fig. 1, where I is the controller’s input, O is the output, C are connection points, S are the sum blocks, and G_i are standard transfer functions.

The control graph is a lightweight and easily modifiable representation of a block diagram, distinct from the diagram itself. Consequently, the nodes do not require a detailed representation of the functional blocks they embody in the Laplace domain. Instead, each node is assigned a numerical code corresponding to a specific functional block, predefined in a functional block library. Table 1 illustrates the functional block library adopted in this work.

2.2. Method for evolving controllers

A parent-child architecture, depicted in Fig. 2, was employed to guide the evolution of the CG, with SA serving as the parent and particle swarm optimization (PSO) functioning as the child. In this setup, SA governs the structural evolution of the graph by managing mutations, while PSO focuses on optimizing the numerical constants embedded within the graph (e.g., the time constants of first-order transfer functions, the gains of the PIDs). The SA algorithm streamlines the control of the evolution process through its temperature-based mechanism and neighborhood definition, eliminating the complexity of establishing a mapping between the graph

Fig. 1. Representation of block diagram as control graph.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the methodology.

structure and numerical parameters – a particularly demanding task for large-scale control graphs. It also allows the human expert to directly review and refine the CG throughout its evolutionary process without depending on additional assumptions.

The pseudo-code for the proposed evolution process is presented in Algorithm 1. The key principles of the SA algorithm [23] are preserved in this adaptation, which employs CGs for knowledge representation. The algorithm explores various neighborhood states through a predefined cooling scheme, updating solutions based on the Metropolis acceptance criterion until a minimum energy state is achieved. This variant diverges from standard meta-heuristic techniques, where solutions are represented as N -dimensional arrays, by encoding the solution as a block diagram within a CG, introducing novel elements, especially in neighborhood design (see Section 2.3). Additionally, it incorporates a *simplification* step, where the CG is analyzed and refined to reduce complexity, enhancing computational efficiency and interpretability of the control system (see Section 2.4).

In Algorithm 1, CG is the control graph, CG_n is the neighbor control graph, T is the temperature of the SA cooling scheme, E is the energy (i.e., fitness function) of the model with CG , E_{new} is the energy of the model with CG_n , K_b is the virtual Boltzmann constant, T_0 is the initial temperature of the SA cooling scheme, k_{max} is the maximum number of

Algorithm 1 Control graph evolution process.

Require: K_b, T_0, k_{max}

- 1: $k \leftarrow 1$
 - 2: $T \leftarrow T_0$
 - 3: Generate the first version of the control graph, CG
 - 4: Compute $E = \text{energy}(CG)$
 - 5: **while** $k \leq k_{max}$ **do**
 - 6: Generate neighbor control graph, CG_n (2.3)
 - 7: Tune numerical constants of CG_n (PSO)
 - 8: Compute $E_{new} = \text{energy}(CG_n)$
 - 9: **if** $p(E, E_{new}, T, K_b) \geq \mathcal{R}(0, 1)$ **then**
 - 10: $CG = CG_n$
 - 11: **end if**
 - 12: Adjust T according to cooling scheme
 - 13: Perform periodical simplification on CG
 - 14: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
 - 15: **end while**
 - 16: Perform simplification on CG
-

algorithm iterations and $p(E, E_{new}, T, K_b)$ is the acceptance probability defined in Eq. (1).

$$p(E, E_{new}, T, K_b) = \min \left(1, e^{-\frac{E_{new}-E}{K_b T}} \right) \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), the Boltzmann constant functions as a hyperparameter that dictates the probabilistic acceptance threshold for suboptimal solutions relative to the current one. Higher values of K_b restrict acceptance to solutions with fitness levels nearly identical to the current solution. Conversely, lower values of K_b allow for the acceptance of solutions with significantly worse fitness.

The cooling scheme of the algorithm is described in Eq. (2).

$$T_{k+1} = \left(1 - \frac{k}{k_{max}} \right) \cdot T_k \quad (2)$$

where k is the current iteration of the algorithm and T_k and T_{k+1} are the temperatures at iterations k and $k + 1$ respectively.

The fitness function should serve as a metric to evaluate the control performance of the generated controller within its application environment (please refer to Sections 3.1 and 3.2.1 for examples). Consequently, both the metric and the modeling details of the environment (e.g., positive sequence modeling, waveform modeling, etc.) – which are decisions typically made by a human expert – must be tailored to the specific control task at hand (e.g., improving frequency stability, transient stability). This aspect of the human-AI interface is essential for achieving rapid and effective convergence to optimal control structures, making existing human expertise a valuable contribution, although not mandatory.

2.3. Generation of a neighbor control graph

In the typical SA framework, transitions to neighboring states (or solutions) occur based on a probabilistic evaluation of the new state's quality, guided by the Metropolis acceptance criterion, and neighborhoods are typically defined using a combination of a predefined distance metric and a random perturbation. However, when the solution is represented as a CG, this generation method of neighbor states becomes more complex. Therefore, inspired by the framework of evolving symbolic models from Ref. [24], a stochastic mechanism that leverages mutation-based operations to generate neighboring candidates effectively is introduced here.

In this scheme, the neighboring CG is obtained by applying a single mutation sampled from a set of mutations predefined by the human user. To sample the mutations, the value of a uniformly generated random number, $U(0, 1)$, is compared with the probability of adoption of each mutation, with a mutation m_j being drawn if the condition of Eq. (3) applies.

$$\forall j, \text{ if } (U(0, 1) < p_{a_j}) : CG_n = m_j(CG)$$

$$\{j = 1, \dots, N_{mut}\} \quad (3)$$

where CG is a control graph, CG_n is the neighboring control graph, p_{a_j} is the probability of adoption of mutation m_j and N_{mut} is the number of mutations.

The mutations used in this work were selected for their ability to create new neighbors and to cover as many transformations as possible that could occur in block diagrams. They are listed in Table 2, where *id* corresponds to the *id* of the node on the graph where the mutation takes place, and the link corresponds to an array [*src*, *out*] where *src* and *out* are the *ids* of the nodes connected in input and output of the new node respectively. The new function is a block with an associated transfer function selected randomly from a function library described in Table 1.

To enhance understanding, Fig. 3 illustrates the neighbor generation process for a CG (right-hand side). Two consecutive mutations are applied: first, the introduction of a new control block ($G3$) in series with the

Table 2
List of mutations of the CG.

Code	Mutation	Parameters
1	Change transfer function on base	id, new function
2	Change transfer function out of base	id, new function
3	Add block on base	id, new function
4	Remove block on base	id
5	Add branch block	link, new function
6	Remove branch block	id
7	Add feedback block	link, new function
8	Remove feedback block	id

base section, and second, the addition of a feedback loop ($link = [4, 3]$). The corresponding changes in the block diagram representations are shown on the left-hand side.

The feasibility of certain mutations depends on the specific configuration of the CG, as some arrangements may permit them while others may not. For instance, modifying or removing a transfer function in a feedback block is impossible if no feedback blocks exist in the CG. Similarly, adding a branch block is not feasible if the CG has already reached the maximum allowable number of branch blocks. As a result, the mutation probabilities p_a are dynamically calculated based on the graph's structure. For instance, a transfer function outside the base can only be altered if the CG contains at least one branch block or feedback block. The calculation of the probability for this mutation is detailed in Eq. (4).

$$p_2 = \begin{cases} p, & \text{if } N_{br} > 0 \text{ or } N_{fb} > 0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where p_2 is the probability of the mutation “change transfer function out of base”, $p = 0.2$, N_{br} is the number of branch blocks and N_{fb} is the number of feedback blocks.

To govern mutations that add or remove blocks in a section of the graph, the probabilities are distributed dynamically. That is, as the number of blocks in a section increases, the probability of adding a block decreases while the probability of removing a block correspondingly increases. This adaptive probability distribution ensures a balanced evolution of the graph's complexity. This evolution of the probability is

Table 3
Adopted size constraints for the control graph. Note that the maximum and minimum numbers of blocks presented in the table do not include the ‘sum’ blocks.

Section	Max n° of blocks	Min n° of blocks
Base	3	1
Branches	1	0
Feedbacks	1	0

illustrated in Eq. (5).

$$p_{add} = \left(-\frac{1}{max - min} \cdot n + \frac{max}{max - min} \right) \cdot p$$

$$p_{remove} = p - p_{add} \quad (5)$$

where p_{add} is the probability of adding a block in a section of the CG, p_{remove} is the probability of removing a block in a section of the CG, $p = 0.2$ on the base section and $p = 0.1$ outside of the base, n is the number of blocks on the section, max is the maximum number of blocks on the section, and min is the minimum number of blocks on the section. Finally, the probability of the last mutation (“change transfer function on base”) is given by Eq. (6).

$$p_1 = 1 - \sum_{i=2}^{N_{mut}} p_i \quad (6)$$

where p_1 is the probability of the mutation “change transfer function on base” and N_{mut} is the number of mutations.

The graphs are subject to several size constraints, as outlined in Table 3, to prevent overly large structures and ensure they remain interpretable for users.

2.4. Control graph simplification

A simplification process is essential to remove unnecessary components and enhance the interpretability of the structure for a human expert analysis. This process consists of two steps, beginning with simplifying individual blocks. Table 4 illustrates the possible simplifications applied during this step.

The second step involves removing gain blocks with a value of $K = 0$ outside the base (branch and feedback blocks) and gain blocks with a

Fig. 3. Illustration of the neighbor generation process in the control graph and the respective block diagram.

Table 4
List of block simplifications.

Original block	Simplified block	Condition
PI	Gain	$K_i = 0$
PD	Gain	$K_d = 0$
PID	PI	$K_d = 0$
PID	PD	$K_i = 0$
PID	Gain	$K_i = 0, K_d = 0$
First order	Gain	$\tau = 0$
Second order	Gain	$\omega_n = 0$
Lead	Gain	$\tau = 0$
Lag	First order	$\alpha = 0$
Lag	Gain	$\tau = 0$
SM	Gain	$H = 0$

Fig. 4. Single-bus electromechanical model of the system modeled in the MATLAB Simulink®.

Table 5
Parameters of the hydropower system.

	Parameter	Value
Governor	T_g	0.5 s
Turbine	T_w	1 s
Swing equation	H	3.5 p.u.
Droop	D	1 p.u.
	R	0.05
Saturation	<i>Upper limit</i>	1 p.u.
	<i>Lower limit</i>	0 p.u.
Rate limiter	<i>Rising slew rate</i>	0.167 p.u.
	<i>Falling slew rate</i>	-0.167 p.u.

value of $K = 1$ on the base. However, if all blocks on the base are gains with $K = 1$, one of them is retained in the CG to ensure that the base contains at least one block.

3. Case studies

3.1. Illustrative example: hydropower system

To illustrate the proposed methodology, a system with a hydropower unit feeding a load in an islanded operation was used. Here, the goal is to enhance the system's frequency stability by designing a controller that performs the transient droop compensation of the hydro-unit. For that purpose, the proposed CG version of the SA algorithm is used to generate a controller that reduces the frequency deviation following a load step. The adopted fitness function, which is shown in Eq. (7), leverages the frequency deviation relative to its nominal value and a penalization term that discourages highly oscillatory responses.

$$\Delta f = \max |f(t) - f_n| + \gamma \cdot \max(0, N_{pk}(f(t)) - N_{pk,max}) \quad (7)$$

where $f(t)$ is the frequency over time, f_n is the nominal frequency of the system, $N_{pk}(f(t))$ is the number of peaks in the frequency signal, $N_{pk,max}$ is the maximum number of peaks and γ is a penalizing constant with the value of 1.10^6 .

The frequency deviation of the hydro-unit is obtained by simulating the load loss in a single-bus electromechanical model of the system modeled in the MATLAB Simulink® graphical programming environment. This model is depicted in Fig. 4 and its parameters are presented in Table 5.

Leveraging the easily established connection between Simulink® and MATLAB® environments, the algorithm described in Section 2 was coded into a MATLAB® script. In the code, the graph is encoded in a class containing an array of nodes and an array of links. Each node has parameters such as *id*, *name*, *base*, and *index* (corresponding section in the CG) and associated functions. The nodes are ordered as shown in Eq. (8).

$$Blocks = [N_1, \dots, N_{N_b}, B_1, \dots, B_{N_{br}}, F_1, \dots, F_{N_{fb}}] \quad (8)$$

where N_i ($i = 1, \dots, N_b$) are the blocks on the base of the graph, N_b is the number of blocks on the base, B_i ($i = 1, \dots, N_{br}$) are the branch blocks, N_{br} is the number of branch blocks, F_i ($i = 1, \dots, N_{fb}$) are the feedback blocks and N_{fb} is the number of feedback blocks.

To distinguish between the contributions of structural design and parameter tuning to system performance, a different metric is introduced for tuning the numerical constants, referred to as the stability margins criterion (SMC). This metric, which is used as the cost function of the PSO, employs two distinct penalty functions, J_{gm} and J_{pm} , to ensure that the gain and phase margins of the system remain within a specified range (see Eq. (9)). In this case, the gain margin is set to be in the range [5, 12] dB and the phase margin in the range [45°, 60°], which are the typical ranges of guaranteed stability for a hydropower system.

To obtain the gain and phase margin of the system, the model of Fig. 4 is linearized and the open-loop transfer function of the system $L(j\omega)$ is extracted. Once the open-loop transfer function is known, the margins can be calculated.

$$SMC = J_{GM} + J_{PM}$$

$$J_{GM} = \max(0, GM_{min} - GM) + \max(0, GM - GM_{max})$$

$$J_{PM} = \max(0, PM_{min} - PM) + \max(0, PM - PM_{max}) \quad (9)$$

where GM is the gain margin of the system in dB, PM is the phase margin of the system in degrees, GM_{min} and GM_{max} are the minimum and maximum values of the gain margin in dB respectively, PM_{min} and PM_{max} are the minimum and maximum values of the phase margin in degrees respectively.

To evaluate the control performance of the PS-CDA-generated controller, the frequency response of the hydro unit to a load step was compared against two benchmark controllers: (i) the standard controller for transient droop compensation proposed in [25], referred to as the *reference controller* (see transfer function in Eq. (10)); and (ii) a controller with the same transfer function, but with parameters re-tuned using PSO based on the SMC, referred to as the *re-tuned reference controller*.

$$G(s) = \frac{\tau s + 1}{\alpha \tau s + 1} \quad (10)$$

For the *reference controller*, the parameters are $\tau = 5$ and $\alpha = 6.5714$, and they correspond to an optimal tuning of the model for islanding conditions [25]. The obtained parameters of the *re-tuned reference controller* are $\tau = 11.1083$ and $\alpha = 7.5998$. The controller learned by the proposed method is depicted in Fig. 6. It consists of a PID ($K_p = 14.6001$, $K_i = 0.4390$ and $K_d = 2.8532$) controller in series with a lead block ($\tau = 20.5622$ and $\alpha = 100$).

The frequency responses of the systems are compared in Fig. 5. The *re-tuned reference controller* exhibits a slightly better frequency deviation than the *reference controller*, but with a slower response. The *PS-CDA generated controller* produces a response showing a higher improvement of the fitness. However, the response is also slower than that of the *reference controller* and with a small overshoot.

This simple example illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed PS-CDA method in learning efficient controllers capable of enhancing system performance. Without prior knowledge, the PS-CDA method identifies a controller with frequency response characteristics better than a controller from the literature. It demonstrates its ability to optimize structural design and parameter tuning.

Fig. 5. Comparison of frequency responses of the three different controllers for the hydropower system.

Fig. 6. Controller learned with the PS-CDA method.

3.2. Grid-forming converter case-study

The case study involves a simple system where a GFM converter is connected to an equivalent representation of the power system, comprising a synchronous generator and a load through a coupling transformer and a transmission line. Similar models have been extensively used in the literature [26,27] for designing GFM-type controls, particularly when aiming to enhance the stability of the power system [28,29]. The single-line diagram of the system considered is shown in Fig. 8, and the key parameters for each component are detailed in Table 6.

3.2.1. Fitness function and system approximation

Similarly to the illustrative example for the hydropower system, the objective of this control is to enhance system stability. Specifically, in this case, the focus is on improving the frequency stability of the existing power system, represented by the synchronous machine and the load. The fitness function from Eq. (7) is employed to achieve this. Here, Δf represents the maximum system frequency deviation experienced by the

Fig. 8. Single line diagram of the test system for the GFM control.

equivalent synchronous machine due to a load step of 0.2 p.u., with the same oscillation penalty applied.

The PSO algorithm, combined with the SMC criterion, tunes the controller parameters. A simplified version of the test system is used when computing the SMC to reduce computational costs and minimize the time required for the PSO to estimate these parameters. This simplified version corresponds to a lighter simulation model where only the system's active power control loops are modeled. This approximation is reasonable, as the primary objective of the control that is to be created is to enhance the frequency stability of the system in response to a load step; therefore, other control loops related to reactive power and voltage control that have a minor impact on the system's behavior [25] can be disregarded. After this step, the frequency deviation Δf is computed based on simulations of the complete digital environment.

3.2.2. Implementation

The test system was modeled in the MATLAB Simulink® graphical programming environment, as depicted in Fig. 7. In the case of the synchronous machine, standard models similar to LCFB1, TGOV2, and AC1A that were parametrized with typical values [30,31] were used to represent the dynamics of the governor and excitation system, respectively.

Fig. 7. MATLAB Simulink® diagram of the grid-forming converter test system.

Table 6
Main Parameters of Test System Elements.

	Load	Synch. Mach.	GFM	Transf.	Line
Sn (MVA)	–	100	20	Sn (MVA)	20
P (MW)	4	4	0	R (Ω)	0.03
Q (MVar)	0.5	0.5	0	X (Ω)	0.39
–	–	–	–	C (μF)	–
					0.13

Table 7
Hyper-parameters.

	Parameter	Value
SA	k_{max}	100
	T_0	$1 \cdot 10^{22}$
	K_b	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-23}$
PSO	N_{iter}	30
	L_s	$\min(20, 5 \cdot N_p)$

Regarding the GFM control system, the components not generated by the proposed method but still relevant to the task have been modeled accordingly. These include a simple volt-var droop control that generates the voltage magnitude reference as a function of the reactive power, an active power limitation control that introduces a negative frequency deviation when the maximum power is exceeded [32], and the converter interface model.

This phase does not consider the converter's current limitation control loop. Since this work focuses on studying power variations and not short circuits, the current can be controlled by controlling the power. Nevertheless, considering the significant influence of the GFM converter's current control dynamics on system response [3], particularly in the context of other types of disturbances (e.g., short circuits), this aspect is currently under research and will be presented as future work.

The GFM converter's primary source is a battery storage system with sufficient available energy to address any existing disturbances. Therefore, no primary source modeling concerns are considered.

The used hyperparameters of the PS-CDA method (i.e., SA and PSO algorithms) are presented in Table 7.

where k_{max} , T_0 and K_b are the hyper-parameters of the SA algorithm as described in Section 2, N_{iter} is the number of iterations of PSO, L_s is the swarm size used in PSO and N_p is the number of parameters to estimate.

Each method run takes an average of 15,355 s on an HP EliteBook 1040 G10 equipped with an Intel® Core™ i7 2.20 GHz processor and 32 GB of RAM. This computation time is considered acceptable, as engineers or operators typically carry out controller design in an offline setting and may take several hours to a few days.

3.2.3. Numerical results

To prove the method's ability to create the control loops for the GFM active-power control and remove its intrinsic randomness, the SA was run 10 times independently, and the evolution of the frequency deviation was recorded. For each of the 10 runs, different seeds were consistently considered for the algorithm. The corresponding fitness curves are depicted in Fig. 10, which also show the frequency deviation when two different benchmarks are used: (i) *reference controller* - a virtual synchronous machine, which is an industry-standard for the active power control loop of GFMs [33], parametrized with typical values $H = 1$ and $D = 30$ from Ref. [34] (ii) *reference controller with re-tuned parameters* - a virtual synchronous machine tuned by minimizing the SMC criterion with PSO. The PSO optimization result gave $H = 3.11$ and $D = 71.94$.

In Fig. 10, the blue curves represent the fitness trajectories for different seeds. All the PS-CDA-based controllers generated across the seeds provide a significant improvement compared to the *reference controller* and a reasonably significant improvement compared to the *re-tuned reference controller*.

One of the 10 block diagrams learned during the validation is depicted in Fig. 11. Within this diagram, the corresponding block of a virtual synchronous machine is identified, similar to the *reference controller*, but with different parameters ($H = 1.04$ and $D = 128.62$). A first-order block is also included with $\tau_1 = 0.03$, in series with the VSM.

Fig. 9. Comparison of system responses for the grid-forming converter test system.

Fig. 10. Fitness curves of the PS-CDA method, and the frequency deviation of the two benchmarks: *reference controller* and *reference controller with re-tuned parameters*.

Fig. 11. Control system learned with the PS-CDA method for the GFM converter.

Additionally, it includes a feedback loop with a first-order block characterized by $\tau_2 = 0.94$. The inclusion of a feedback loop is noteworthy, as it helps reduce errors and enhances system stability.

The temporal evolution of key system variables for this block diagram is depicted in Fig. 9, along with the corresponding system responses for the two benchmark configurations for comparison. The green, red, and blue curves correspond to load disturbances of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 p.u. respectively. Both the *re-tuned reference controller* and *PS-CDA generated controller* demonstrated a significantly improved frequency deviation for all disturbances. The *PS-CDA generated controller* achieved a significantly better fitness than the *re-tuned reference controller*. This improved frequency response results from a faster and more pronounced power response that arrests the frequency deviation at greater speed. Although the power can sometimes exceed 0.2 p.u., the duration of this peak is very short as the maximum power control takes action.

4. Conclusions

This work presented a novel methodology for automated control design in power systems by leveraging SA for the structural evolution of the controller and PSO for parameter tuning, and introducing a flexible and interpretable graph-based representation of control systems.

Two case studies validated the methodology: hydropower and GFM-based power systems. In the illustrative hydropower example, the *PS-CDA-generated controller* demonstrated superior stability compared to the *re-tuned reference controller* and a frequency deviation comparable to the *reference controller*. In the GFM case study, controllers generated by the PS-CDA method consistently outperformed the re-tuned benchmark and the reference benchmark configurations regarding frequency stability. The results highlight the PS-CDA method's capability to learn efficient controllers without prior knowledge while ensuring interpretable solutions, representing a step towards automating the design of control systems. A more comprehensive comparison between the learned model and reference models for different fault types is planned for future work.

Despite these promising results, there are various topics for future research: a) extend the framework to enable interactive learning between

humans and AI by allowing human experts to refine the design during data-driven learning based on domain knowledge, thus balancing automation with human oversight; b) extend the framework to incorporate additional constraints, such as hardware limitations or current saturation in converters; c) integrate advanced AI techniques, such as pre-trained large language models, which could improve the optimization of the control structure by leveraging pre-existing knowledge in the literature (e.g., see [35]); d) perform comparative analysis with alternative approaches such as ANN and GP, as well as explore potential hybridization strategies, e.g., how ANN can be integrated as a functional block alongside traditional PID controllers, leveraging the strengths of both data-driven and model-based control paradigms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lucas Bost: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Francisco S. Fernandes: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Ricardo J. Bessa: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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